

Methodological and Ideological Options

Designing MEMME – A conceptual material and energy metabolism model for economies

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ABSTRACT

Energy and materials drive the socioeconomic processes of the economy, acquiring economic value through physical and chemical transformations. Consequently, understanding an economy requires analyzing not only its monetary flows but also its biophysical flows and stocks. However, integrating material and energy perspectives into a unified analytical framework remains a challenge that existing approaches have only partially addressed. This study introduces the Material and Energy Metabolism Model for Economies (MEMME), a new conceptual biophysical model that provides a consistent and balanced accounting in both mass and energy units. MEMME focuses on material, energy, and food and feed transformations, integrating stocks and flows, to enable a more comprehensive analysis of social metabolism. It presents new indicators that improve our understanding of resource use, transformation efficiency, and their connection to economic activity, including a biophysical economic productivity indicator (BioEP), which measures how effectively physical outputs (materials and useful exergy) contribute to generating economic output. The Portuguese case study (1970–2022) shows that resource use increased and stock grew, while efficiency gains were modest and did not reduce overall consumption. BioEP reveals that Portugal became more efficient at converting resources into useful flows, but less efficient at translating those flows into economic value, highlighting a tradeoff between efficiency and productivity. BioEP, however, also indicates absolute decoupling between 2000 and 2008. MEMME provides a consistent framework to derive such integrated insights.

1. Introduction

An integrated biophysical perspective on social metabolism is necessary to understand economies' interactions with the environment and internal dynamics. Socioeconomic metabolism (SEM) provides this framework by viewing societies as complex socio-natural systems (González de Molina and Toledo, 2023; Victor M. Toledo, 2011). Inspired by the biological metabolism concept; it recognizes that societies depend on material and energy flows for operation and reproduction (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999; González de Molina and Toledo, 2023). It analyses the biophysical flows exchanged between societies and their surrounding environment (i.e., natural resource

inputs and waste and emission outputs), as well as the SEM flows within the socioeconomic systems (Fischer-Kowalski and Haberl, 1997; Haberl et al., 2019). These flows sustain biophysical structures (material stocks), e.g., buildings or machinery, and together with material and energy flows provide services like mobility, shelter or supply and discharge for society.

Although flows of materials and energy are closely related in SEM, empirical metabolism research mostly looks at materials or energy while integrated perspectives are rare (Giampietro et al., 2009; Haberl, 2001; Krausmann et al., 2004). On one hand, Material Flow Accounting (MFA) compiles material inputs (e.g., domestic material inputs) and tracks material stocks and outputs, including waste and greenhouse gas

Abbreviations: CAP, Common Agriculture Policy; BioEP, Biophysical Economic Productivity; EU, European Union; FAO, Food and Agriculture Organization; GDP, Gross Domestic Product; IEA, International Energy Agency; MEMME, Material and Energy Metabolism Model for Economies; MEFA, Material and Energy Flow Accounting; MFA, Material Flow Accounting; MISO, Material Inputs, Stocks and Outputs; MuSIASEM, Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism; SEM, Socioeconomic Metabolism; SEA, Societal Exergy Accounting; UNEP IRP, United Nations Environmental Programme's International Resource Panel.

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emissions (Krausmann et al., 2017a). On the other hand; Societal Exergy Analysis (SEA) studies quantify the primary (e.g. crude oil extraction); final (e.g. electricity); and useful (e.g., lighting) stages of energy flows; enabling the assessment of aggregated efficiencies (Pinto et al., 2023; Sousa et al., 2017).

Studies have integrated energy and material accounting within the SEA framework, recognizing that exergy—the potential of a given quantity of energy to perform work—can be a unifying metric for both energy and material flows. Wall (1977) first used this approach and computed the exergy efficiency for Sweden; Italy and Japan (Wall, 1990; Wall, 1987; Wall et al., 1994). While focusing on energy and material transformations in SEM; these studies excluded “loops” in flows such as recycling flows; due to the energy-centered perspective. More recently; Carmona et al. (2021) extended this approach by including all natural resources (namely modern renewables e.g., solar and wind power). They also included feedback flows and divided resources into food, technical energy, and material conversion categories. However, the focus on material and energy transformations was lost, making it difficult to identify where they occur in SEM and to calculate their efficiencies. For example, determining the efficiency of material production becomes difficult, as the final exergy is part of the technical energy chain, while produced materials fall under the material conversion chain.

While energy is represented via the mass of energy carriers (biomass, fossil materials) within MFA, the immaterial forms of energy are excluded i.e., most modern renewable energy sources, like hydro, wind or solar power. The representation of energy flows in units of mass also does not adequately reflect the “energy value” of these materials. A similar issue can be pointed to accounting only in exergy units as the embedded exergy of a material does not fully express its value, because exergy does not properly reflect the material use. Additionally, chemical exergy varies by type of material (Michalakakis et al., 2021) which leads to results that appear “distorted” when compared to mass perspective results.

The treatment of energy and materials by choosing a single unit, also ignores their interdependence and non-substitutability when it comes to service provision. Three key energy-material links can be identified: a) extraction, processing and transport of materials require energy; b) energy infrastructures and conversion technologies require materials; and c) the provision of services from material stocks (e.g., rail system; rail cars and locomotives) require energy.

There are approaches that aim to integrate energy and material perspectives, such as the Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) model (Giampietro et al., 2009) and the Material and Energy Flow Analysis (MEFA) framework (Krausmann et al., 2004).

MuSIASEM provides a multi-scale perspective to analyze energy and material flows by defining the socioeconomic system distinguishing between funds (structural elements that remain over time and that are responsible for energy transformations) such as capital, people and land and flows (transient inputs/outputs) such as food. It distinguishes between endo and exo-somatic metabolism and uses time (in hours) to provide a unified metric, e.g., energy and materials consumed per hour of work across scales. While it reveals cross-scale dependencies, its treatment of material flows is less detailed than energy, weakening full energy-material integration. Additionally, the energy is quantified only up to the primary or final stage – not to the useful stage and transformation efficiencies are not quantified. MEFA is a framework that accounts for all inputs and outputs of SEM flows, from MFA and EFA (Energy Flow Accounting). EFA differs from traditional energy balances because it also considers food energy and livestock-related biomass (Haberl, 2001). While MEFA argues for the need to consider both material and energy flows, it ultimately keeps the accountings separate, not allowing a true energy-material integration.

Integrating both energy and material perspectives remains a challenge when considering the limitations of previous studies by analyzing energy and materials separately, keeping the accounts of both ultimately

separated or aggregating them using a single unit.

In this study, the challenge is addressed through a novel approach which maintains the specific characteristics of materials and energy in SEM while integrating both perspectives within one accounting framework. The accountings in mass and energy units are kept fully consistent and balanced. The Material and Energy Metabolism Model for Economies (MEMME) is a biophysical conceptual model focused on material and energy transformations inherent to SEM, combining material recirculation/recycling and stocks with energy and material flows.

MEMME is developed conceptually and applied to a national case study covering 1970–2022 (with some data only available until 2016). Portugal was selected due to the extensive datasets available, including SEA and material-stock studies. Over this period, Portugal underwent major energy and economic shifting from oil to natural gas and later to renewables for electricity (Felício et al., 2024); alongside a structural shift of the economy (services contributing 76% of gross value added in 2022; up from 55% in 1970) (European Commission, 2024). Political changes, such as the end of dictatorship in 1974 and entering the EEC (European Economic Community) in 1986, also shaped Portugal's SEM, affecting resource substitution, transformation efficiencies, and energy-material-economy linkages.

Focusing on a transition period is crucial not only for understanding Portugal's SEM evolution but, also, for offering insights into other economies undergoing similar shifts. This case study encompasses over four decades to provide a comprehensive historical perspective.

Section 2 presents MEMME development and its components. Section 3 shows the application to the case study, while the discussion of results and conclusions are drawn in section 4.

2. MEMME: premises, boundaries and structure

MEMME focuses on energy and material transformation processes in SEM, through the accounting of flows from primary resources to the disposed waste and emissions, while including the stocks. The principles of the model, namely system boundaries and structure, were defined to frame all SEM flows based on three key premises:

- All processes or stocks (which are represented by boxes) are energy and mass balanced,
- Processes/transformations only occur within boxes, so flows have the same value from origin to destination,
- Flow values are kept in mass and energy units whenever possible.

Maintaining energy and mass units allows a consistent accounting of all flows and allows different indicators to be estimated in the same transformation process (see subsection 2.3).

2.1. System boundaries

MEMME investigates stocks and flows of energy and materials in a socioeconomic system (e.g., a national economy). Fig. 1 shows the structure of MEMME. The socioeconomic system is embedded in the natural environment (the green “background” layer), from which all natural resources are extracted (materials, energy carriers) or harvested (solar radiation) and where all outflows of wastes and emissions, including dispersed heat, are discarded to. The investigated socioeconomic system also exchanges flows of materials and energy with other socioeconomic systems (e.g. other national economies) as import and export flows from/to markets, which are shown as trapezoids located on the socioeconomic system boundary.

2.2. Structure and concepts

MEMME structure includes transformation boxes (rectangles), stock boxes (round-corner rectangles), market boxes (small trapezoids) and flows (arrows). There are four types of flows distinguished by the type of

Fig. 1. Material and Energy Metabolism Model for Economies. The green box is the natural environment. Grey rectangles are transformation boxes, blue round-cornered rectangles are stocks, white parallelograms are trade markets, oval shape includes end-uses (transports, households and commercial and public services). Flows: the dashed line is the system boundary, black full lines are material flows (flows quantified in mass and energy, if possible), grey full lines are energy flows (flows quantified only in energy), dotted lines are waste and emissions flows and dash-pointed lines are trade flows. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

line and colour of the arrows: black full lines are material flows, grey full lines are energy flows, dotted lines are waste and emission flows and dash-pointed lines are trade flows. The flows represented in grey correspond to immaterial flows that can only be measured in energy units.

2.2.1. Transformation boxes

In the MEMME context, a transformation is a process that requires energy and materials for a physical and/or chemical change of the resource. The MEMME structure was developed around three main transformations: Energy (box 2), Material (box 3) and Food and Feed (box 4). A fourth box is considered (box 1) where resource gathering occurs through harvest or extraction.

All transformations related to the energy flow chain are considered energy transformations and include conversions such as, e.g., the potential energy of water in a dam into electrical energy and the chemical energy in a fuel that is combusted into the mechanical energy of a motor. So, from the primary stage of natural resources (e.g. crude oil or wind) to the final stage where it is available for the final consumer (e.g. diesel or electricity), and further until the end-use where each type of useful exergy (e.g., heat or mechanical drive) will provide a service (e.g., thermal comfort or transport), all conversions of energy occur in the energy transformations, box 2. This includes energy transformations that occur in several infrastructures and machines such as solar farms, refineries, power plants, car motors, electric heaters, stoves, etc. As it encompasses all the energy transformations, the energy transformations' box corresponds to the extended energy sector proposed by Santos et al. (2025).

Energy is quantified in terms of exergy because it enables the consistent aggregation of energy flows of different thermodynamic quality, such as heat and mechanical or electrical work, by expressing them in a common unit of "mechanical work potential" and allows

efficiencies to be meaningfully aggregated across heterogeneous conversion processes (Felício et al., 2019).

Useful exergy is defined as the minimum amount of final energy, or electricity, required to obtain a given amount of useful energy. For example, the exergy of 1 kWh of heat at 80 °C in an environment at 10 °C is the amount of electricity an ideal heat pump would need to supply it under those conditions, i.e., about 0.2 kWh, whereas the exergy of 1 kWh of electricity is 1 kWh.

Material transformations include all chemical and physical processes that change a material's form, its composition, or combines it with other materials to create new ones (except those that are considered under energy and food/feed transformations). This includes transformations that typically occur within the manufacturing industries, e.g., wood into furniture or paper, iron into steel, metal ore into metal alloys, oil products into plastics, natural gas into ammonium, etc. These materials are transformed to produce products and stocks (further described in subsection Stocks) which are used in SEM by final consumers to provide services along with useful exergy, e.g., a car is a stock that uses useful exergy, as mechanical drive, to provide the service of transportation.

Food and Feed transformations, box 4, includes all transformations related to consumable goods for humans or animals, as well as the production of animal by-products for non-food industries, e.g. rendered animal fat for lubricants or leather for the textile industry. Food and feed are a source of energy and material for humans and animals (Sousa et al., 2008). Therefore, food and feed processes are kept separately from the other two types of transformations. The slaughter of animals and the bottling of beverages are also included in this box.

Harvest and Extraction, box 1, is where material resources are harvested (biomass) and extracted (minerals, crude oil and natural gas). All "non-material" energy forms (solar, wind) are represented as the "Primary exergy from Renewables" flow. The transformation in box 1 is the process of taking the resources from their natural environment and

preparing them as they enter the socioeconomic flows, e.g., separating a metal ore from the tailings or the washing and cutting of the roots from crops. Harvesting is the process of obtaining biotic resources from the biosphere, from ecosystems managed by society (agriculture, forestry and fisheries) where reproduction of resources can be controlled by humans (except for wild hunting and fishing). Extraction involves locating and retrieving energy carriers and materials from the lithosphere (mining and quarrying). Humans cannot control resource reproduction as it occurs in the lithosphere, and the resources are considered non-renewable as they do not reproduce within a human lifespan nor shorter periods.

2.2.2. Stocks

Three distinct stocks are represented in MEMME: Livestock (box A), Population (humans, box B) and Material Products and Stocks (box C).

Livestock and Population are autopoietic entities that can process food and feed and reproduce autonomously. They are subject to the natural processes of population renewal through reproduction and migration (including imports and exports of livestock). Livestock includes all domesticated animals, including animals for food and other products, draft power or other services, as well as fishing stocks (aquacultures and wild) and game. Population includes all human individuals that inhabit within the socioeconomic system boundaries (e.g., the population living in a country or a region).

Material Products and Stocks are the man-made result from the material transformations. Material products are all short-lived products which are used within a one-year lifespan, e.g., disposable packages and hospital-use products. Material Stocks comprise all stocks of artifacts including all built structures, stationary machinery, vehicles and all other durable goods with an average lifetime longer than one year. They are required for transformation processes, having a structural functionality, and in MEMME, are represented as a separate box for reasons of practicability — not all stocks can be unambiguously allocated to each transformation box with current detail available in the data —.

2.2.3. Flows

Domestic raw material extracted or harvested is considered a material flow, as these resources are harnessed as materials and transformed for energy, material or food and feed uses.

Raw materials for energy transformations are, thus, material. However, as both energy (PJ) and mass (Mt) units are kept, the energy transformation efficiencies across the system can be computed, corresponding to SEA's primary-useful exergy efficiency. All energy is accounted for in exergy. All energy transformation outputs, except exports and byproducts, are useful exergy that is provided and consumed in the other boxes (1,3,4 and 5) in the form of heat, mechanical drive, electrolysis, light, electronics and cooling. Thus, those outputs can only be accounted for in energy units.

All material transformations' inputs and outputs are considered material except for the useful exergy needed for the transformation processes, e.g., mechanical drive for a machine in a factory. The outputs are all represented as material and accounted for only in mass units due to the complexity of material mix of some material products, that makes it very difficult to convert mass into exergy.

Byproducts that flow from box 2 to 3 have non-energy uses, e.g. oil products from refineries to produce plastics. These outputs are accounted for in energy and mass units but are represented in MEMME as materials.

Food and Feed inputs and outputs are represented as material flows. These flows are not quantified in energy units because processed food, feed and by-products for non-food uses are made of several types of materials and, thus, difficult to convert into exergy. Therefore, all consumable goods and byproducts from box 4 are classified as materials in MEMME. Nevertheless, there are efforts to account for food in exergy (e.g., Manso et al. (2018) and Meng et al. (2022)) which could make the full accounting in both units possible in the future.

The trade flows (imports and exports) are represented by Markets.

A precise description of each flow is available in Table 1. Flows are named as in Fig. 1 and labelled according to the flow's origin and destination boxes, e.g. useful exergy (E) provided from box 2 to box 3 is identified as flow F_{2_3E}. Distinction between flows with the same origin and destination is made with an extra letter: F – fertilizer, E – useful exergy, P – products, S – stocks and W – waste. NE denominates an origin/destination in the natural environment.

Further considerations regarding MEMME flows:

- All fossil fuels in their primary forms (crude oil, coal and natural gas) are included in flow F_{1_2}, as in MEMME it is considered they are first extracted for energy transformations;
- Biofuels such as biodiesel, biogasoline and bio jet fuel are included in F_{3_2p}, as they result from processes using vegetable oils and by-products from box 4 (F_{4_3}), e.g., animal fats, and from other processes occurring in box 3. Therefore, it is considered that these bio-fuels are produced in box 3 and flow to energy transformations box ready to be used;
- Recycling and downcycling processes occur within the material transformations box. The reused materials flow (F_{C_3}) enters as an input, and the recycled materials market, e.g. metal scrap, is included in Market 3. Thus, imported materials for recycling are an input to material transformations box, while exports are an output. If a material is directly exported without any transformations previous to that, it enters box 3 in the F_{C_3} flow and exits to Market 3, to be exported without any transformations.

2.3. Stock-flow interactions in MEMME

For a clear understanding of MEMME's perspective on SEM, two short examples are provided to illustrate the conceptual model.

Transformations require not only flows of energy and materials, but also, material stocks. For example, in car chassis production (material transformation), metal sheets (input of materials) are heated (input of heat) and placed into pre-made molds (material stock), where they solidify. The machinery and the pre-made mold are in material stocks (box C), the conversion of electricity into heat that occurs in the electric furnace is included in energy transformations (box 2), and the transformation of the metal sheet into a chassis shape as it solidifies again is in material transformations (box 3).

As a more complex example, consider industrial agriculture. All tools and machines are classified as material stocks. The conversion of energy used to operate these machines (e.g., diesel for a reaper) into mechanical drive takes place in box 2. The resulting mechanical work—e.g., cutting grain crops—is a flow into the harvesting process (box 1), as reaping is part of this process. Then, outcome of agricultural activities, such as harvested grain becomes available as raw material. After trade (Market 1), the harvested crops flow to boxes 3 or 4; e.g., grain used for food and feed transformations moves to box 4. The produced feed and food then flow to Livestock (box A) and food to Population (box B), respectively.

These examples illustrate the reasoning behind the MEMME structure, showing that:

- a) Material stocks integrate every step of metabolism that requires infrastructure and machinery,
- b) SEM is a dynamic process that progresses over time. However, available data is usually aggregated yearly, omitting detail that would only be visible in smaller time steps. The idea of a continuous perspective on SEM has been explored in other studies, e.g., Schiller et al. (2017),
- c) Some material stocks cannot be assigned to a single transformation box. For example, a machine with a robotic arm used in microchip production serves functions in both the energy and material transformation boxes (2 and 3). In box 2, it converts electricity into mechanical drive, while in box 3, its robotic arm places specific

Table 1

List of MEMME flows with label and description. Flows are identified by corresponding label on the model according to the flow's origin and destination boxes. For flows with common origin-destination labels, a letter is added to specify the flow: F – fertilizer, E – useful exergy, P – products, S – stocks and W – waste. NE denominates an origin/destination in the natural environment.

Flow	Flow resources	Flow label
Grazed biomass	Biomass consumed directly as feed by livestock without transformations.	F_NE_A
Livestock manure	Manure from livestock used as organic fertilizer, including manure left on pastures and manure applied to soils (such as manure treated and manure from bedding and deep bedding).	F_A_NE _F
Animals for slaughter and raw animal products	All live animals to be slaughtered, fish catch (wild and from aquaculture), game meat and raw animal products that don't require the animal's death, e. g., eggs, raw milk and wool	F_A_4
Domestic raw material	Biomass harvested as crops and wood, as well as all minerals extracted including mineral oil (crude oil), coal, metal ore and non-metallic minerals. Natural gas and waste used as raw material (e.g., for biogas production) are also included.	F_NE_1
Market 1 trade	This is a bidirectional flow, which corresponds to the imports and exports of raw material and primary. Its value (+imports-exports) shows if the socioeconomic system is a net importer or net exporter.	F_1_M1
Primary exergy from renewables	All energy stored in renewable sources (except biomass), i.e. potential energy in dams, kinetic energy in wind, heat from geothermal sources and solar radiation, kinetic energy from waves and tides.	F_NE_2 _E
Raw material transformations	Biomass harvested to be consumed directly as an energy carrier to transform into other forms of energy (e. g., electricity in a power plant or heat in a fireplace). All fossil fuels in their primary forms, i.e., crude oil, natural gas and coal. Minerals used for nuclear energy, e.g., uranium, are also included.	F_1_2
	Biomass harvested for material purposes, e.g., crops for non-food use or wood for furniture; animal products used for non-food uses, e.g., raw wool; and all minerals for material products and stocks, e.g. sand and gypsum.	F_1_3
	All primary crops (crops that have not undergone any transformation further than preparation for primary market, e. g., washing of fruits and vegetables) for food and feed uses.	F_1_4
Market 2 trade	Similar to F_1_M1 but for the trade of electricity and energy carrier products, e.g. oil products for refinery.	F_2_M2
Useful exergy	Useful exergy consumed for harvesting in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, as well as for extraction in mining and quarrying.	F_2_1
	$F_{2,1} = F_{2,1_{hvt}} + F_{2,1_{ext}}$	
	Useful exergy consumed for material transformations, typically occurring in the manufacturing and construction industries.	F_2_3 _E
	Useful exergy consumed for food and feed transformations, typically occurring in food and tobacco industry. Slaughterhouses consumption is included.	F_2_4
	Useful exergy consumed in transport, households, commercial and public services.	F_2_5

Table 1 (continued)

Flow	Flow resources	Flow label
Muscle Work	Useful exergy produced by Livestock in the form of muscle work for different activities, e.g. in agriculture for plowing.	F_A_1 _E , F_A_3 _E , F_A_4 _E
	Useful exergy produced by Population in the form of muscle work for different activities, e.g. in construction of buildings.	F_B_1, F_B_3, F_B_4
By-products	By-products resultant from energy transformations but used to produce material products and stocks (e.g., hydrocarbons from refineries to produce plastics and natural gas to produce ammonium).	F_2_3 _P
	By-products resultant from material transformations, e.g., black liquors and biodiesel.	F_3_2 _P
Non-food products	Products resultant from food and feed transformations used for material transformations to produce non-food uses, e.g., lard for lubricants and pyrethrum extract for medicinal products.	F_4_3
Market 3 trade	Similar to F_1_M1 but for the trade of raw, semi-finished and finished products for material transformations. This includes trade with secondary raw materials (e.g., scrap) and recycled materials contained in traded products.	F_3_M3
Short-lived products	Material products used within a 1-year period lifespan and, thus, not part of material stocks, e.g., chemical fertilizers and pesticides.	F_3_C _P
Addition to material stocks	New materials that accumulate in Material stocks (e.g., concrete in built structures or wood in furniture) with a lifetime longer than 1 year – Gross addition to stock.	F_3_C _S
Reused materials	Recycled and downcycled materials produced during industrial processes, material stocks degradation and products post-consumption.	F_C_3
Waste for energy	Industrial waste (F_3_2 _W) and municipal waste (F_C_2) used for incineration.	F_3_2 _W and F_C_2
Market 4 trade	Similar to F_1_M1 but for the trade of food and feed products, including raw animal products.	F_4_M4
Market A trade	Similar to F_1_M1 but for the trade of live animals.	F_A_MA
Seeds	Transformed biomass for seeding (i.e., seeds are collected while crops undergo transformation processes).	F_4_NE
Feed	Transformed biomass consumed by livestock (e.g., forage, silage and hay).	F_4_A
Food	Transformed biomass consumed by population (e.g., bread, pasteurized milk and cooked potatoes).	F_4_B
Waste	Residues from harvest, mining and quarrying, e.g. foliage, straw, tailings and slurries.	F_1_NE
	Managed waste, e.g., waste sent to landfill, and unmanaged waste such as stock in hibernation, e.g., building ruins.	F_C_NE
Waste and emissions	Feed waste, emissions and dejects (not used as organic fertilizer) from feed metabolization.	F_A_NE _W
	Food waste, emissions and dejects (usually as sewage sludge) from food metabolization.	F_B_NE
	Dispersed heat and waste to be disposed of from energy transformation processes.	F_2_NE
	Dispersed heat, emissions and waste to be disposed of from material transformation processes.	F_3_NE

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Flow	Flow resources	Flow label
	Dispersed heat, emissions and waste to be disposed of from food and feed transformation processes.	F_4_NE _w

components within the microchip. So, some material stocks cannot be confined to one transformation box, thus, the need for a separate material stocks box (box C) for practical and simplification reasons.

MEMME is currently a territorial, production-based accounting framework in which the national system is represented as an aggregation of lower-level processes. Aggregate exchanges within the system and with the rest of the world are tracked, but spatial relationships are not explicitly resolved.

2.3.1. Indicators

By integrating the perspectives of SEA and MFA, MEMME enables the quantification of shared indicators from these approaches and new indicators focused on energy-material interactions. In supplementary material A, tables A-1 and A-2 summarize SEA and MFA indicators, their equivalents in MEMME.

Table 2 shows new indicators enabled by MEMME's perspective. A detailed explanation of each is in subsections following the table. These indicators provide insights into SEM dynamics by keeping these transformations central to the discussion, which emphasizes interactions within the socioeconomic system, as well as interactions with other systems and the natural environment. This is important because energy and materials become socioeconomically useful only after undergoing physical or chemical transformations.

2.3.2. Extraction (I_{ext}) and Harvest (I_{hvt}) exergy intensities

Looking at the intensity of resource gathering is important as it represents the initial interaction between socioeconomic flows and the

$$\varepsilon_E = \frac{\text{Useful exergy} + \text{Exports} + \text{Byproducts}}{\text{Raw Material} + \text{Primary exergy from Renewables} + \text{Imports} + \text{Byproducts} + \text{Waste for energy}} \quad (3)$$

natural environment. This set of indicators explores the energy-material dynamics of resource gathering through extraction and harvest by

$$\eta_M = \frac{\text{Short-lived products} + \text{Material stocks addition} + \text{Byproducts} + \text{Exports} + \text{Waste for energy}}{\text{Raw material} + \text{Reused materials} + \text{Imports} + \text{Byproducts} + \text{Non-food products}} \quad (4)$$

evaluating the useful exergy necessary to obtain 1 Mt of resource.

The extraction intensity indicator, I_{ext} is the ratio of the useful exergy consumed in Mining and Quarrying (F_{2_1ext}) to the extraction output flow before trade (Market 1):

$$I_{ext} = \frac{\text{Useful exergy consumed in Mining and Quarrying}}{\text{Extraction output}} \quad (1)$$

These flows are input and output of box 1.

Similarly, the Harvest intensity indicator, I_{hvt} , is the ratio of the useful exergy consumed in Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (F_{2_1hvt}) to the harvest output and animal products' flows before trade. Harvest is considered in a broader meaning, and unlike the previous indicator, I_{hvt} requires an additional flow that does not interact with box 1. This is because energy data on Agriculture includes both crop and livestock production justified by the fact that a lot of agricultural systems are indeed a combination of both, reporting both activities at once. For a consistency matter, Fisheries are also included in this indicator, as aquaculture is a part of agriculture as well. Therefore, flow F_{A_4} of animals for slaughter and animal products (which includes fish catch and aquatic products), an input to box 4, is included in this indicator.

$$I_{hvt} = \frac{\text{Useful exergy consumed in Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries}}{\text{Harvest output} + \text{Animal products}} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the intensity of agriculture is actually also computed within I_{hvt} , rather than the intensity of harvesting only.

2.3.3. Transformations' efficiencies: Energy (ε_E), Material (η_M) and Food and Feed (η_{FF})

The efficiencies of the transformation boxes reflect how effectively the socioeconomic system utilizes its available resources. This offers a dimensionless measure of how close the system is to fully use its resources - or, from another angle, how much waste (including dispersed heat) is produced from those resources.

The efficiency of energy transformations (ε_E) is given by the ratio of the output to the input flows in box 2. Similarly, the efficiency of material transformations (η_M) corresponds to the ratio of output to input flows in box 3, while the efficiency of food and feed transformations (η_{FF}) is given by the ratio of output to input flows in box 4.

$$\eta_{FF} = \frac{\text{Feed} + \text{Food} + \text{Seeds} + \text{Non-food products} + \text{Exports}}{\text{Raw Materials} + \text{Animal products} + \text{Imports}} \quad (5)$$

2.3.4. Material transformations exergy intensity (I_M)

The exergy intensity of material transformations indicator, I_M , is used to capture the dependency of industrial processes on exergy consumption, emphasizing the link between energy and material flows. Similar to extraction and harvest intensities, I_M is given by eq. 6:

$$I_M = \frac{\text{Useful exergy for material transformations}}{\text{Short-lived products} + \text{Material stocks addition} + \text{Byproducts} + \text{Exports} + \text{Waste for energy}} \tag{6}$$

2.3.5. Biophysical economic productivity (BioEP)

Useful exergy is the stage of the energy chain closest to economic value. Similarly, material products and stocks in use are the closest to economic value production. Together, useful exergy with material products and stocks in use provide services (e.g., sustenance, thermal comfort, transport). Thus, an indicator relating these with GDP intends to capture the dynamic of these three components of SEM: material, energy and economic value.

This new indicator (Eq. 7) is the economic output generated per unit of combined material (stocks and products) and exergy outputs – the biophysical output. These outputs result from all transformation processes (boxes 2, 3 and 4) within the SEM and either provide societal services within the socioeconomic system or are exported. The biophysical outputs are defined accordingly with the output approach of GDP, where the intermediates used to produce the outputs are subtracted to avoid double counting of the resource outputs, e.g. steel is accounted as a material output while the electricity used in the electric arc furnace to produce it is not.

$$BioEP = \frac{GDP}{\text{Material Outputs}^{1/2} * \text{Useful Exergy}^{1/2}} \tag{7}$$

BioEP reflects how efficiently the socioeconomic system transforms physical resources into economic value.

Both terms of denominator are powered to 0.5 to guarantee that when an economy is simply a scaled-up version of another (e.g., double the GDP, double the material outputs, and double the useful exergy), the BioEP remains the same. The geometric mean is commonly used in composite indicators, such as the Human Development Index (UN Development Programme, 2024), to avoid full compensation and reduce sensitivity to outliers. In BioEP, it is considered that exergy and materials are complementary rather than substitutable and all values are normalized by indexing to a base year, allowing a simpler comparison over time.

Following Semieniuk (2024), decoupling within a single country should be assessed using territorial national-accounts GDP at constant prices, rather than PPP- or exchange-rate-based measures, which are designed for cross-country comparisons. However, periodic structural revisions to national accounts can substantially revise historical GDP

Table 2
New indicators drawn from applying MEMME's approach.

New MEMME indicators	Units
Extraction exergy intensity	PJ/Mt
Harvest exergy intensity	PJ/Mt
Energy transformations efficiency	% (PJ/PJ)
Material transformations efficiency	% (Mt/Mt)
Food and Feed transformations efficiency	% (Mt/Mt)
Material transformations exergy intensity	PJ/Mt
Biophysical economic productivity	M\$/√(Mt*PJ)

growth and, consequently, decoupling results, making these indicators partly dependent on accounting conventions. We therefore use territorial national-accounts GDP in constant 2015 U.S. dollars from the World Bank, based on national statistical sources. These data are expressed in constant prices, meaning they are inflation-adjusted with 2015 as the reference year. The World Bank provides several GDP “vintages” under these conditions, and we use the December 2024 release as there are no differences on GDP vintages from 2021 onward.

All the presented eqs. (1 to 7) are included in supplementary material B, specifying all flows of each equation.

3. Portugal through the lens of MEMME (1970–2022)

As the structure and key concepts of the model are defined, the application to a case study provides an in-depth look onto it. Portugal from 1970 to 2022 underwent several transitions that impacted its socioeconomic metabolism, being a good case study. Portuguese population has increased by circa 2 million people, between 1970 and 2022, up to 10 million inhabitants, while its livestock has decreased by approximately 0.6 million LSU (livestock units), reaching 1.9 million LSU in 2022 ((FAO, 2024; United Nations, D. of E. and S.A.P.D, 2024)) as there has been a transition towards smaller animals (e.g.; poultry) in livestock production. The land for agriculture remained relatively constant at 42–43% (FFMS, 2025).

In 1986, Portugal entered the European Economic Community (EEC), now European Union (EU) (European Union, 2025); which brought along big investments in infrastructures and buildings during the 1990s while the population exodus from rural parts of the country towards the coastal cities kept on going since the 1960s. This required more construction and; thus; more materials. The demand for construction increased as the country transitioned from a focus on the secondary economic sector in the 1970s to an economy centered on the tertiary sector (Mitchell, 2007).

Portugal's GDP per capita has steadily grew from 7670 US\$ in 1970 to 22,043 US\$ in 2022 (constant prices 2015 US\$). Although it remained below European Union average, Portugal become part of World Bank's group of high-income countries in 1994 (World Bank, 2024). During the study period; however; high fiscal deficits and subsequent economic crises led to IMF bailouts in 1983 and 2011 (International Monetary Fund, 2021). Portugal recorded its first fiscal surplus since 1992 only in 2023.

3.1. Data

The data gathered for this case study was sourced from international databases whenever feasible. This was done to ensure that MEMME can be applied across countries using existing and comparable data while enabling the computation of all relevant flows for short-run studies. Whenever possible, data was gathered from databases specialized in the subject, such as IEA database for energy flows and FAO database on crops, livestock and food. UNEP IRP Global Material Flows database was used as a source for the extraction and trade of minerals and metals and other materials not covered by other sources (e.g. grazed biomass); data regarding material stocks and the corresponding flows was sourced from MISO2 database (Plank et al., 2022; Wiedenhofer et al., 2024). An exception are the non-metallic minerals, which had to be reversed engineered from MISO data, as data was overestimated in UNEP IRP database. Outflows of waste, dispersed heat and emissions were not

Fig. 2. Input flows to MEMME transformation boxes, Portugal 1970–2022. 2A: Input flows to Energy Transformations (box 2). 2B: Input flows to Material Transformations (box 3) – only until 2016 due to data availability. 2C: Input flows to Food and Feed Transformations (box4). All flows denoted with “Imp” before the name are imports from each respective market. Exports are not shown in this figure as they are outputs of each box.

Fig. 3. Harvest and Extraction exergy intensities, Portugal 1970–2022.

quantified because these flows are only partially covered in available data sources.

A detailed table with the data sources per flow, including the specific datasets, and methodological notes on more disaggregated categories within the flows is available in supplementary material C.

3.2. Portugal's biophysical and monetary indicators

3.2.1. Biophysical flows and indicators

MEMME derived indicators in Table 2, are computed once the biophysical flows have been accounted for. Fig. 2 characterizes the Portuguese economy's demand for resources, showing the input flows to all transformation boxes after Market 1, including raw material for transformations' flows (F_1_2, F_1_3, F_1_4 and F_A_4), flows between boxes (F_2_3p, F_3_2p, F_4_3) and all import flows except for Market 1 (F_2_M2, F_3_M3 and F_4_M4).

In Fig. 2A it is highlighted that oil and oil products are the main raw material / energy resource flow to box 2. Portugal made the transition to oil as the main energy resource in the 1970s, with big investments such as the Sines' refinery that started functioning circa 1972, moving afterward towards coal, due to the high oil prices (Felício et al., 2024). Natural gas appears in the Portuguese energy system only in 1997; imported from Algeria; substituting mostly coal. In the early 2000s; the investment in modern renewable sources; i.e. wind and solar power; rapidly grew so that in 2010 harnessed renewables (F_NE_2) were the main source of electricity production (ibid). This corroborates previous studies that highlight Portugal's energy transitions supported by government policies and investments (Felício et al., 2024; Felício et al., 2019).

Portugal has always been a net importer of raw materials and primary crops, Market 1, which is shown in detail in supplementary material D. Regarding energy transformations, this is relevant because all fossil fuels consumed in Portugal are imported. The pandemic influenced the material inputs accentuating the downwards behavior after 2017, mostly due to lower imports of crude oil. Coal disappears in 2020 when the last coal powerplant closed. The increase in primary solid biofuels (biomass) by 1988 occurred due to a data review done by IEA, leading to a "jump" in consumption compared to previous years.

Fig. 2B shows that non-metallic minerals have been dominating the raw material flow F_1_3 into material transformations since 1970. Their input surpassed all other materials combined by 1975, increased until 2000, and declined sharply afterward, predominantly due to the decrease in consumption of non-metallic minerals for construction (United Nations Environment Programme et al., 2025). The inputs of

industrial roundwood have been relatively constant through the five decades, while non-food primary crops (e.g. manila hemp and natural rubber) have not been relevant throughout the whole period analyzed. An increase in the imports of fossil fuel products, namely for plastics, and of recycled and downcycled materials is shown from 1998 onwards, mostly for recycled materials.

Regarding Fig. 2C, primary crops' inputs have steadily increased, as the economy and population grew, while the increase in imports of other edible products has also been significant, as the consumption of animal products and processed/secondary products (animal and plant-based) have significantly increased, since the late 1980s, after Portugal's modernization and EU-entry, as the country stopped being so commercially isolated with the dictatorship end.

Harvest and Extraction exergy intensities

Harvest exergy intensity, I_{hvt} in Fig. 3, more than doubled from 1970 to the mid-2000s as result of agricultural intensification. This trend is consistent with global evidence showing that, since the 1970s, exergy inputs per ha increased, largely driven by the use of fertilizers, pesticides, irrigation, and associated mechanization (FAO, 2024; USDA Economic Research Service, 2025). This modernization of methods has been closely linked to the rise in land productivity (Steenwyk et al., 2022). When Portugal joined the EU in 1986, it came under the Common Agriculture Policy (CAP), with the 1992 reform considered weak concerning cereals and biased towards livestock agriculture – specially milk production (Pereira and Martinho, 2017). In Portugal, this was reflected in rising in milk production and a slight decrease in crops share of the total agricultural output, in mass (from about 90% to 80% in 2000 (FAO, 2024)). At the same time, European funds allowed investment in irrigation systems which increased maize production that peaked (in tons produced) around 2000 (Viana et al., 2021). After that, the 2003 CAP reform led to a decrease in production in southern Portugal due to farm abandonment and continuous shift from arable to permanent crops and livestock (Pereira and Martinho, 2017), and a relative stabilization of I_{hvt} afterwards.

The exergy intensity of extraction, I_{ext} , remained relatively stable until 2000, when it began to increase. This shift is linked to a rise in the extraction of non-ferrous metallic ores, diminishing the relevance of less energy-intensive non-metallic minerals used in construction (from less than 10% of total extraction in 2000 up to ca. 17% in 2014).

3.2.2. Energy and material transformation efficiencies

Transformation efficiencies' indicators offer an overview on how close the system is to fully use its resources (domestic origin and imported), showing that in the Portuguese economy case, that ability has

Fig. 4. Portuguese efficiencies of energy and material transformations (ϵ_E and η_M respectively), 1970–2022. Series on η_M are only 1970–2016 due to data availability constraints.

Fig. 5. Material transformations exergy intensity of the Portuguese economy, 1970–2016.

been relatively stable with a slight increase in material transformations.

Fig. 4 shows the energy and material transformations' efficiencies, ε_E and η_M for the period under study. Food and feed transformations' efficiency, η_{FF} , was not computed due to data restrictions as FAO datasets on Food and Feed for the period 1970–2022 were only available in primary-crop equivalents. This hinders the computation of an efficiency which provides meaningful results, because it does not allow a comparison of the output's real mass with the input's mass. An alternative calculation using energy units was not considered because only food data was available in kcal. Therefore, authors opted to not include this indicator's results.

Energy transformations' efficiency, ε_E , differs from SEA primary-useful exergy efficiency because it includes outputs with non-energy uses, such as naphtha (i.e., flow F_2_3p). Despite the transition towards a more electrified economy and shifts in the mix of energy carriers used for electricity generation, ε_E has remained relatively constant at around 14% throughout the entire period. Notably, electricity has played a significant role in Portugal's energy consumption since approximately 1986, when end-use electrification reached around 36% (Felício et al., 2024).

The efficiency of material transformations, η_M , has been constantly increasing since 1976 from around 80% to values above 85% from 1986 onwards. This increase was first driven by the use of non-metallic-construction materials including concrete and large amounts of sand

and gravel and a declining significance of the domestic processing of metal ores. The F_3_Cs flow of materials towards stocks had a 6-fold increase from 1970 to 2000, mostly because of concrete use which had a 4-fold increase in mass terms and was the largest mass flow to material stocks until 2000 representing over 50% of F_3_Cs (Wiedenhofer et al., 2024). This was due to the big investments in construction of buildings and infrastructures after Portugal joined the EU. Between 1996 and 2003, there is a small decline as the share of metal ores in input flows increased slightly (Fig. 2), which are associated with production processes of low efficiency. After 2003, as investments slowed when Portugal transitioned to euro currency and the use of concrete saw a substantial decline, reliance on aggregates of virgin materials (i.e., sand) and of recycled/downcycled materials increased and pushed the η_M upwards. In fact, recycled and downcycled materials almost doubled from circa 5.9 Mt./yr to 13.2Mt/yr, as shown Fig. 2 B, which represented a 4-fold increase in the share of secondary materials in total inputs to material transformations from circa 5% to 20%. At the same time, flows of asphalt, plastics, wood and paper products grew their relevance within F_3_Cs flow substantially (combined, from about 25% in 2003 to roughly 55% of the total material to stocks' flow), contributing to the continuous increase in efficiency as these products' production processes are more efficient than of cement and concrete production. There are more fluctuations in efficiency in later years, in 2004 due to a peak in inputs of mixed/complex products imports, and in

Fig. 6. Biophysical economic productivity (BioEP) of the Portuguese economy, 1970–2016, indexed to the year 1970.

Fig. 7. Portugal's material stocks (black), useful exergy outputs (blue) and material outputs' (orange) economic productivities 1970–2016. GDP in 2015 US dollars. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

2016 due to a drop in the exports of products mainly from non-metallic minerals. As isolated points, these could also be due to trade data flaws or inaccuracies.

3.2.3. Material transformations exergy intensity

The material transformations exergy intensity, I_M , shown in Fig. 5, quantifies the useful exergy used to produce a unit of material output, e.g., 1PJ/Mt indicates that producing 1Mt of material outputs requires 1PJ of useful exergy in the industrial sector (material transformations, box 3).

Until 1995, I_M varied between 0.9 and 0.6 PJ/Mt per year. The years with the lowest value of I_M around 2000 coincide with the periods when the use of concrete, which is a less exergy intensive material, peaked. However, since 2001, while material production has decrease significantly, the decrease in useful exergy consumption has been much smaller leading to the exergy intensification of material production in Portugal. This trend is largely driven by the structural change in the addition to stocks' flow F_{3_C} , from construction materials (large mass flows to relatively small energy requirements) to manufacturing (other industries, e.g., Paper and pulp, which has a material transformations' exergy intensity of circa 16 PJ/Mt). The sudden doubling of I_M after 2010 shows a coupling of useful exergy and material in Portugal's material transformations.

3.2.4. Economic indicators

Economic productivities quantify the capacity of economies to generate output from resources' use, providing a complementary perspective to social metabolism analysis with an output-oriented perspective.

Fig. 6 shows the biophysical economic productivity indicator, BioEP, indexed to 1970 as the base year. Material and useful exergy outputs (biophysical outputs) in 2016 were generating only 80% of 1970's economic output and BioEP decreased afterward reaching 0.57 in 2001. Until 2016, it increased continuously but never reached the same productivity as 1970 (BioEP = 1 again). This means there was more economic value added to the biophysical outputs, including stocks produced, in 1970 than in 2000 or 2016. This is directly related to the material stocks generated and accumulated over time, which, in turn, are linked to where useful exergy is consumed, all resulting from the investments made during that period.

Portugal's GDP grew from 1970 to 2022, with exception for the 2008–2013 recession (World Bank, 2024) while its biophysical throughputs, materials and useful exergy were being used to produce long-lived material stocks. Material stocks add to national capital and

contribute indirectly to support economic activity throughout their lifespan but are only directly reflected in GDP when first built or later depreciated. GDP mainly reflects the turnover of short-lived products or the direct use of useful exergy. In Portugal, until 2001, biophysical outputs grew faster than GDP, generating progressively less economic value per unit of throughput, largely due to large-scale investments in concrete-intensive infrastructure and housing, coupling biophysical outputs with annual economic output and pushing down BioEP. After 2001, as additions to material stocks began to shift towards shorter-lived products and stock building slowed, biophysical outputs decreased until 2014 while GDP remained broadly stable. This led to a rise in BioEP, although not to the same level as in 1970. In Fig. 7 this is indicated by an almost doubling of material outputs' economic productivity after 2001. Apart from the recession period GDP increased over time, material consumption has declined since 2001 and useful exergy consumption has stabilized, indicating an absolute decoupling of SEM outputs (exergy and materials) from economic growth for the periods 2000–2008.

However, these decoupling results should be interpreted with caution. As noted by Semieniuk (2024), structural revisions to GDP series can affect historical growth rates and thus the measured extent of decoupling. Moreover, MEMME indicators are production-based rather than consumption-based, meaning that part of the observed decoupling in 2001–2014 could, in principle, reflect the relocation of material- and energy-intensive activities abroad through trade rather than a true reduction in the biophysical requirements of Portuguese consumption. This interpretation aligns with the literature on ecologically unequal exchange (Hornborg, 1998; Hornborg and Martinez-Alier, 2016), which emphasizes the displacement of resource extraction and environmental pressures through global trade. However, in the case of Portugal, the material footprint, a consumption-based indicator, shows absolute reductions (INE, 2025), suggesting that externalization is unlikely to be the dominant driver of the observed decoupling.

The decrease in stocks' economic productivity is shown in Fig. 7, where there is a continuous decrease reaching in 2016 less than half of 1970 productivity (1970: 0.13\$/Mt*yr, 2016: 0.63\$/Mt*yr). This means that twice the amount of material stocks was required to support 1\$ in GDP. However, from 2012 onwards, a slight stabilization occurs, similar to the trend observed between 1984 and 1988. The more recent stabilization of stocks can be attributed to the plateau in stocks from 2012, while GDP continued to grow.

Krausmann et al. (2017b) observed on a global scale, that material stocks productivity decreased slightly between 1970s to 2010, while the material use productivity (here material outputs) increased. A similar trend is observed for Portugal for both indicators.

4. Discussion and conclusions

To overcome the limitations of existing approaches, MEMME fully integrates material and energy perspectives while maintaining their distinct characteristics. It offers a mass- and energy-balanced framework that simultaneously accounts for material and energy flows, including both tangible (e.g., fossil fuels, biomass) and intangible forms (e.g., wind, solar, nuclear), across all transformation stages (primary, final, and useful). Unlike conventional approaches that either isolate materials or energy or aggregate them in a way that obscures their specific roles, MEMME explicitly tracks transformations (physical and chemical), feedback loops (e.g., recycling), and the energy-material-service links. It enables the analysis of efficiencies within transformation chains, such as material production or energy conversion, by clearly locating them in socioeconomic metabolism. MEMME also integrates stocks and flows, ensuring that material infrastructures and energy systems are both represented.

MEMME adds new indicators that help better understand how society uses and transforms natural resources. Harvest and Extraction intensities measure the useful exergy required to obtain a mass unit of biological or geological resources, respectively, while transformations' efficiencies, including energy, material, and food and feed efficiencies, evaluate how effectively the system converts inputs into economically valuable or useful outputs for society. Indicators such as transformations' efficiencies, used at such high scale (country-level), can pinpoint and reinforce the need for more detailed studies on lower scales, such as at the sectorial or product levels, to provide a better understanding of results, showing the relevance of a comprehensive study on social metabolism at all scales. Complementing the indicators mentioned, the Material transformation's exergy intensity quantifies the energy intensity of industrial transformations, while the Biophysical economic productivity indicator, BioEP, evaluates the effectiveness of converting biophysical outputs (material and exergy) into GDP. Together, these indicators improve our understanding of how resources are used, how efficiently they are transformed, and how they relate to economic activity.

The Portuguese economy grew as population and material stocks increased. This is also reflected in the rise of exergy and material inputs (Fig. 2) not only to support growth but also to sustain a larger and more complex socioeconomic system. Exergy intensities of harvest, extraction and material transformations more than doubled, while the efficiency of energy transformations remained approximately constant and the efficiency of material transformations increased. This suggests an economy with a social metabolism more dependent on consumption of biophysical resources at the end of the period (2016) than in 1970.

In the 1960s, industry was already slightly less significant than services, and its share in GDP began to decline from the mid-1970s onward, while the contribution of services to GDP surpassed 50% in the mid-1970s and continued to expand steadily in Portugal, reaching around 75% by 2010 (PORTDATA, 2024). Throughout this structural transition; both material and useful exergy consumption increased (Cunha and Ferrão, 2022; Felício et al., 2024; Niza and Ferrão, 2006). This transition appears to have largely concluded in the early 2000s, when the growth of exergy and material use slowed, indicating a shift towards more stable levels of resource consumption. During this period, the efficiency of energy transformations remained relatively constant (Fig. 4): efficiency gains through continuous electrification were offset by the growing relevance of less efficient end uses linked to the expansion of services such as low-temperature, e.g., cooling systems like air conditioners (Felício et al., 2024). In contrast, the efficiency of material transformations increased (Fig. 5), mainly driven by changes in the material mix, as the decline of metal-ore processing and the growing use of concrete, aggregates, recycled materials, and materials with lower transformation losses (e.g., asphalt, plastics, wood, and paper) progressively raised efficiency. However, material production also shifted towards more exergy-intensive materials, often short-lived goods (e.g.,

petrochemical products, paper, vehicle parts), partially offsetting these efficiency gains.

Overall, resource use increased, and key indicators of resource intensity deteriorated, while efficiencies improved only moderately. This pattern is contrary to the dominant narrative of technological progress, which assumes that rising resource efficiency is the basis for the decoupling of resource use from economic development. Such decoupling is often presented as a pathway to achieve climate targets without radical changes in consumption patterns, however, contradicted by the collective of these results.

MEMME provides a way to look at decoupling through the estimation of the biophysical economic productivity at the useful stage (BioEP). From 1970 to 2001, biophysical throughput at the useful stage remained coupled to economic value, whereas the period 2001–2014 was characterized by absolute decoupling from economic growth. This corresponded to BioEP declining during the 1970s and again in the 1990s, reaching its lowest value around 2001, increasing afterwards to levels lower than 1970, showing an overall decline. The observed decoupling trends in Portugal after 2001 are also reflected in the development of material footprint data, which is available from the International Resource Panel (United Nations Environment Programme et al., 2025). These data show that between 2003 and 2013 Portugal experienced absolute reductions not only in domestic extraction (DE) and domestic material consumption (DMC), but also in the consumption-based material footprint indicator. The decline of both territorial and consumption-based indicators suggests that the decoupling observed in our results is not primarily driven by the externalization of material intensive processes to other countries and imports. Part of the absolute decline observed between 2008 and 2013 can be attributed to the economic recession and the associated period of weak economic growth, a pattern that has been widely documented in the literature which shows that absolute decoupling is often closely linked to periods of low or negative economic growth (Shao et al., 2017; Steinberger et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2019). Overall, a comparison between 2016 and 1970 shows that Portugal's socioeconomic metabolism became more efficient at converting resources into useful flows, but less efficient at translating those flows into economic value.

While MEMME is applied here at the national level, its accounting structure is not inherently tied to that scale. MEMME can be applied to regions, metropolitan areas, or urban systems, allowing the analysis of urban–rural metabolic linkages, regional specialization, and intra-national inequalities in material and energy use. Such applications would make it possible to explore how different territories contribute to and depend on the national metabolism, although they would require detailed data.

This study has some limitations. The analysis of the *Food and Feed transformations* and its associated indicator could not be fully explored due to a lack of raw data, specifically, real product weights rather than their equivalents in primary crops. This type of data was previously available from FAO but has been withdrawn from datasets since methodological changes were introduced in 2010.

The fact that MEMME presents a perspective for a consistent accounting of energy and mass makes it pivotal to deal with data inconsistencies between sources. This is associated, not only with the lack of information regarding the systems where data is taken from but, also, with the fact that detailed data is made available by specialized institutions focused on one perspective. Two examples make this clear: data on wood from IEA is inconsistent with FAO data (methodological options of this study to surpass this difficulty are described in supplementary material C), while bitumen data on trade from UN Comtrade reveals a possible underestimation from IEA trade data (Plank et al., 2022).

As a conceptual model, MEMME highlights the challenges related to consistent data accounting for social metabolism, previously identified by Müller et al. (2018). Available data often lacks comprehensive descriptions of the systems and conditions under which they are collected,

resulting in inconsistencies across data sources and making it difficult to draw cohesive and robust conclusions. Despite these challenges, MEMME addresses the two key recommendations outlined by Müller et al. (2018) for models and scenarios aimed at monitoring the physical economy. First, by providing a consistent and integrated accounting framework for energy and materials, MEMME enables an improved definition of energy and material constraints for use in emission models. Second, by maintaining mass and energy units throughout the analysis, MEMME improves system understanding by exploring the links between energy and materials, thereby supporting more accurate scenario forecasting.

An important direction for future research is to link MEMME indicators to economic growth and well-being in a way comparable to the exergy-growth literature (Ayres and Warr, 2005). While previous studies based on Societal Exergy Analysis focus on final-to-useful exergy efficiency and useful work (Santos et al., 2025; Santos et al., 2018; Serrenho et al., 2016), MEMME provides a broader view by jointly accounting for exergy and material flows. Future work integrating MEMME into macroeconomic frameworks would therefore allow a more complete assessment of how material-energy systems contribute to economic performance and well-being.

Also, while this paper is focused on presenting MEMME and its associated biophysical indicators, following Requena-i-Mora and Brockington (2021) who emphasize that sustainability indicators reflect particular worldviews and distributions of environmental burdens, future work should combine MEMME with consumption-based measures of both materials and energy, such as the material footprint and embodied-exergy indicators. This would help assess not only whether observed decoupling reflects real global reductions in resource use or mainly a shift of impacts abroad, but also how environmental pressures and benefits are distributed across territories.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Laura Felício: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fridolin Krausmann:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Tânia Sousa:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2026.109059>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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